

DIFFICULTIES OF PARENTS WITH LOW EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT IN ASSISTING THEIR CHILDREN IN MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING DURING PANDEMIC

JOHN G. LOBO¹, APRIL JOY D. DACULA², APRIL ROSE C. INSO³, NANETTE M.
MENDOZA⁴, MARGIE L. TESORO⁵

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3023-5439>¹, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8258-1254>²,
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6452-5239>³, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5570-0088>⁴,
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4841-5809>⁵,

johnbryan0326@gmail.com¹, apriljoydacula0@gmail.com², aprilrose.inso@deped.gov.ph³,
nanettemanubag24@gmail.com⁴, margietesoro9@gmail.com⁵,
Zamboanga Peninsula Polytechnic State University Zamboanga City, Philippines

ABSTRACT

A significant role was played by the parents of the students, who had to become home schoolers within a few days without prior training upon the suspension of face-to-face education. Thus this study investigated the difficulties of 90 parents with low educational attainment in assisting their children in modular distance learning. In-depth analysis and survey were employed as research instruments to extract responses on the difficulties of parents with low educational attainment and how government should aid them during a global crisis. The research findings showed a high prevalence of intellectual problems where parents struggled to explain, elaborate, and understand the lessons in the SLM. Simulated teacher roles were another difficulty where parents were clueless on facilitating home schooling and addressing learners' needs. It further revealed gender roles difficulties where women tend to assumed the home schooling responsibilities added to increasing discrepancies of roles in child and home care. Most of the families belong to low-income households and experienced economic difficulties on added expenses incurred in assisting their children in implementing modular distance learning. Results dictated that government can support the parents by equipping them to be effective collaborative partners in the new modality through developing skillset on learner's management, strategies on administering learning modules, remote instructional support to bridge the gap in learning and intensify programs venturing in livelihood and entrepreneurial opportunities. This study is vital to map out the difficulties of parents with low educational attainment in modular distance learning. It initiates responses by providing them concrete home schooling manuals, module guides, training, and programs, establishing effective partners in the collaborative process of continuous learning at home.

Keywords: COVID-19 Pandemic, Parents, Educational Attainment, Difficulties, Intellectual, Roles, Economic, Philippines